

Exploring the *In Vivo* biodistribution of ambient-stored Technetium-99m Labeled Methylene Diphosphate (^{99m}Tc-MDP) Radiopharmaceutical aliquots in Infected Rat Models

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Technetium-99m methylene diphosphonate (^{99m}Tc-MDP) is widely used for detecting skeletal metastases, infections, and other metabolic bone disorders. However, radiopharmaceutical wastage and dependence on cold-chain storage limit access in low-resource oncology settings. This study evaluated the radiochemical stability of fractionated MDP aliquots stored under ambient, refrigerated, and frozen conditions to identify cost-effective strategies for improving availability.

A controlled true-experimental laboratory study was conducted at the University Teaching Hospital Nuclear Medicine Hot Laboratory in Zambia. Forty aliquots from fractionated MDP kits were stored under ambient (25–42 °C), refrigerated (2–8 °C), and frozen (–23 °C) conditions. Each aliquot was radiolabelled with ^{99m}Tc and assessed for radiochemical purity (RCP) using instant thin-layer chromatography, with ≥90% as the WHO acceptance threshold. Ambient-stored aliquots meeting this criterion were further evaluated in infected rat models using planar scintigraphic imaging.

All four normal saline ambient-stored aliquots-maintained RCP values of 98–99% for up to 18 days, while refrigerated and frozen samples retained 99–100% for up to 28 days. All seventy-two (72) samples of aliquots met WHO standards. A total of twelve (12) rats were used to test biodistribution. Imaging confirmed higher tracer uptake in infected tissue, indicating preserved functional integrity.

These findings suggest that MDP fractionation and ambient storage are feasible, cost-effective approaches for reducing wastage and improving nuclear medicine access in resource-limited settings.

Keywords: Technetium-99m, Methylene Diphosphonate, Radiochemical Purity, Nuclear Medicine, Bone Scintigraphy, LMICs.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Technetium-99m methylene diphosphonate (^{99m}Tc-MDP) is a commonly used radiopharmaceutical for detecting skeletal metastases, bone infections, and other metabolic abnormalities of the skeleton (1,2). Despite its clinical importance, significant radiopharmaceutical wastage and dependence on cold-chain storage systems continue to constrain access to nuclear medicine services in many resource-limited oncology settings. Infectious Diseases due to microorganisms like *staphylococcus aureus* are a global issue, underdeveloped nations account for most of the 13 million infectious illness deaths per year (3). In 2001, infectious illnesses caused 26% of worldwide mortality and 26% of disease burden (4, 5). The increase in antimicrobial medication resistance has made the treatment of infectious illness even harder (6,7) Thus, every effort must be made to correctly diagnose infectious illnesses. Although there are a number of laboratory tests to detect infections, use of radiopharmaceuticals can be applied to trace deep seated diseases in the body like cancers and infections (9,10). This is because, radiopharmaceuticals generate ionizing radiation from specific region of interest thereby making the procedure more sensitive and precise resulting in increased diagnostic confidence. Given that accurate diagnosis of infectious diseases often relies on highly sensitive radiopharmaceutical imaging to detect deep-seated infections, any compromise in cold-chain storage can reduce radiochemical stability and tracer effectiveness, ultimately undermining diagnostic accuracy and clinical decision-making. Radiopharmaceuticals have improved medicine services,

providing precise diagnostic capabilities and innovative treatments for a wide range of ailments. These radiopharmaceuticals, consisting of a radioactive isotope combined with a pharmaceutical compound, offer exceptional precision when it comes to diagnosing and treating various medical conditions (11). Radiopharmaceuticals are widely used in diagnostic imaging procedures as single-photon emission computed tomography (SPECT) or positron emission tomography (PET) among others; the precision of these imaging techniques allows healthcare professionals to identify and evaluate various ailments with accuracy (12). While radiopharmaceuticals offer remarkable accuracy in diagnosis and treatment, several challenges exist (13). These include the short half-lives of certain radioisotopes, limited availability, and cost considerations. Other challenges come in when there is low patients' volume, low Tc radionuclide dose against a whole multidose vial of MDP radiopharmaceutical kit that can cater for a good number of patients tends to go to waste. Literature has shown that MDP aliquots stored at refrigerated and frozen remain viable for as long as 9 months (14,15). Fractionation method makes radiopharmaceuticals cheaper, more accessible, and less wasteful. The effects of ambient conditions on aliquots in areas with unreliable cold chain backup strategies have barely been studied. The MDP radiopharmaceutical is one of the commonly used radiopharmaceutical kits in Nuclear Medicine. It is used to diagnose infections among others. Therefore, this study assessed the quality and biodistribution of ambient stored MDP radiopharmaceutical kit aliquots made from normal saline.

2.0 MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was approved by the Zambia National Health Research Authority ((Ethical approval No: NHRA0000015/01/06/2022) and by Excellence Research Ethics and Science Converge (ERES) ethical committee. One type of Normal Saline (NS) by dissolving 0.5g of stannous chloride into a packet of 500ml NS while the other one was purged with argon gas and augmented with stannous chloride (NSSCl₂) while the other one remained as initially prepared (NSSCl₂A). These two streams were labelled as such and kept in an ambient environment whose temperature ranged from 16°C to 38°C. This study therefore aimed at optimizing the use of MDP radio-pharmaceutical by exploring the quality at ambient conditions in low resource settings with cold storage challenges.

2.1 Preparation of MDP aliquots

Two MDP Radiopharmaceutical kit vials were reconstituted with 4 ml of the four types (streams) Normal Saline (NS) namely; NS, argon purged Normal Saline (NSA), Argon purged Normal Saline with Stannous Chloride (NSSnCl₂A) and Normal Saline with Stannous Chloride (NSSnCl₂). 1 ml was extracted from each of the four MDP radiopharmaceutical kit vial and stored in sterile vials. Each stream of NS consisted of 20 aliquots; one ml aliquot from each stream (two aliquots total) was refrigerated (2–8°C), while the other two were frozen (below 0°C). These 4 aliquots kept at frozen and refrigerated conditions were considered as controls since they were kept at recommended conditions according to literature. The remaining 36 aliquots, 18 from each stream were kept at ambient conditions for 18 days.

2.2 Quality Control

After elution of Technetium, 1 vial of MDP aliquot was labeled with Technetium, quality control tests on the ambient stored aliquots were done every day according to their age from day 1 on aliquot 1 up to day 18 on aliquot 18 on all the four NS streams. Twelve (12) healthy 30–65g rats that had never been subjected to research were separated and placed in clean cages. These rats were given clean water and fed with proper food throughout the experimental period.

2.3 Radiochemical Purity (RCP) Test

The RCP test involved using two strips of Whatman paper, measuring 0.9 cm by 8.5 cm. These strips were marked to indicate the origin (1 cm from the bottom) and the solvent front line (6.5 cm from the origin). A drop (0.05 ml) of Technetium-labeled MDP aliquots was applied at the origin on two separate chromatographic paper strips. These strips were then submerged in two different mobile phases, Normal Saline and Methyl Ethyl Ketone (MEK). The mobile phases facilitated the separation of various components in ^{99m}Tc-MDP, including radiochemical impurities and the anticipated radiochemical compound. The radiochemical impurities included free Technetium pertechnetate (^{99m}TcO₄⁻) and the colloid, hydrolyzed reduced pertechnetate (^{99m}TcO₂). Whatman paper served as the immobile phase, while MEK and normal saline were employed as the mobile phases. Two chromatography paper strips were placed in separate developing chambers containing MEK and normal saline after the application of 0.05 ml of ^{99m}Tc-MDP at the origin line. Free ^{99m}TcO₄⁻ is soluble in both NS and MEK, thus migrated with the mobile phase as the paper became wet until the expected spot. In contrast, ^{99m}TcO₂ is insoluble in sodium chloride and soluble in MEK hence migrated with MEK solution but remained stationary with NS as a mobile phase. Once the solvent reached the solvent front line, the strips were removed and allowed to dry. After drying, each strip was cut in half, and the activity of the strips was measured using a dose calibrator. This measurement helped calculate the RCP using a manual method. It's worth noting that the RCP of ^{99m}Tc-MDP must not be less than 90%.

2.4 Creation of Infected Rat Models for biodistribution studies

Biodistribution studies of ^{99m}Tc -MDP radiopharmaceutical aliquots were conducted in both uninfected and infected rat models. Each rat received an intravenous injection via the tail vein of ^{99m}Tc -MDP at a dose ranging from 7.4 to 18.5 MBq (0.2–0.5 mCi) in a volume of 0.1–0.3 mL. The aliquots selected for this study included those prepared with stannous chloride, which exhibited the highest radiochemical purity (RCP), and those prepared from the plain normal saline stream, which showed the lowest RCP. The resulting biodistribution patterns were then compared between infected and control groups.”

To induce infection, 12 rats were used. Out of the 8 were scuffled to attain full control, anaesthetized by making them sniff diethyl ether-soaked cotton wool (according to institutional Veterinary Welfare) and later inoculated with human and porcine *S. aureus* bacteria suspension into the left thigh bone (18, 19). four rats were not inoculated with any staphylococcus aureus, were isolated and treated as controls. The infected rats were kept up to fourteen days while being monitored daily to ensure food availability, clean water and surroundings. On day three and nine, the rats were contained in a glass enclosure, made to sniff diethyl ether-soaked cotton wool for anesthesia, then ^{99m}Tc -MDP made from the MDP aliquots was injected into the tail vein. The ^{99m}Tc -MDP was administered at least two hours prior to imaging to allow for adequate biodistribution. Following this period, biodistribution studies were carried out using a planar imaging system. The planar-computer system automatically generated images showing the distribution of ^{99m}Tc -MDP in both infected and uninfected rat models.

3.0 RESULTS

Table 1 below shows a comparison of the average RCP for different MDP aliquots kept at ambient conditions to those kept at recommended conditions (Frozen and refrigerated once-off).

Table 1: RCP of ^{99m}Tc -MDP aliquots made from all streams of NS and kept at recommended conditions

Aliquot stream	Aliquot age (days)	Storage Temp. (°C)	Average RCP (%)	Comment
NS	28	-23	100	Passed
	28	3	99	Passed
	18	27	98	Passed
NSA	28	-23	100	Passed
	28	2	99	Passed
	18	27	99	Passed
NSSCL ₂	28	-23	100	Passed
	28	2	100	Passed
	18	27	98	Passed
NSSCL ₂ A	28	-23	100	Passed
	28	2	100	Passed
	18	27	99	Passed

Figures 1 and 2 illustrate the comparison of radiochemical purity (RCP) between two pairs of normal saline streams: NSA versus NS, and NSSnCl₂A versus NSSnCl₂.

Figure 1: RCP of ^{99m}Tc -MDP aliquots reconstituted with NSA and with NS.

Figure 2: RCP of ^{99m}Tc-MDP aliquots reconstituted with NSSnCl₂A and NSSnCl₂

3.1 Rat images comparing the biodistribution of ^{99m}Tc-MDP

The use of ^{99m}Tc-MDP prepared from ambiently stored NSSnCl₂ (figure 3) exhibited a good biodistribution in region of interest. The resultant images following biodistribution studies indicated a high concentration of ^{99m}Tc-MDP in the left thigh for infected rats one and two compared to the uninfected one. This is illustrated by darker spots in region of interest (left thigh) compared to the non-region of interest. Due to the limitations of the planar imaging system and the exploratory nature of this study, quantitative region-of-interest (ROI) analysis was not performed. Nevertheless, the observed increased uptake in the infected left thigh compared to the contralateral and control regions consistently indicated preferential localization of ^{99m}Tc-MDP in infected tissues. We have now clarified this limitation in the manuscript and recommended that future studies incorporate semi-quantitative methods, including ROI-based target-to-background ratio analysis, to strengthen the objectivity and reproducibility of imaging findings.

Figure 3: Biodistribution images of control and infected rats with *s. aureus* after being injected with ambiently stored ^{99m}Tc-MDP aliquots made from the NSSnCl₂ stream

3.2 Rat images comparing the biodistribution of ^{99m}Tc-MDP prepared from ambient ally stored NS stream aliquots

The use of ^{99m}Tc-MDP prepared from ambiently stored NS exhibited a good biodistribution in region of interest (Figure 4). The resulting images following biodistribution studies indicated a high concentration of ^{99m}Tc-MDP in the left thigh for infected rats one and two compared to the uninfected one. This is illustrated by darker spots in region of interest (left thigh) compared to the non-region of interest.

Figure 4: Biodistribution images of control and infected rats with *s. aureus* after being injected with ambiently stored ^{99m}Tc -MDP aliquots made from the NS stream in posterior position

4.0 DISCUSSION

The findings from this research revealed that MDP aliquots kept at room temperature remained viable for eighteen days with RCP of 98% to 100%. The use of freshly prepared normal saline and controlled handling conditions may have minimized oxygen exposure and contamination, thereby preserving the reducing environment required for stable labeling and also the presence of stannous chloride (Sn^{2+}) as a reducing agent plays a critical role in maintaining radiochemical integrity by preventing oxidation of technetium and minimizing the formation of free pertechnetate ($^{99m}\text{TcO}_4^-$) and hydrolyzed reduced technetium ($^{99m}\text{TcO}_2$). These factors collectively contribute to the sustained high RCP observed even under ambient conditions. The RCP testing method used a manual calculation approach with dose calibrators and were read immediately after drying. The RCP readings were close to each other with inter-strip variability.

The ^{99m}Tc -MDP radiopharmaceutical localized in the target location after two hours. The rats were imaged under a nuclear planar machine, and the computer automatically generated images. The biodistribution studies showed successful localization of ^{99m}Tc -MDP as highly concentrated hot spots were seen in the region of interest (rat infected left thigh bones). The biodistribution studies of ^{99m}Tc -MDP radiopharmaceutical aliquots were compared between the non-infected rats as the control, human and pig infection rat models post-inoculation on days three and nine. The ^{99m}Tc -MDP was prepared from NS stream aliquots which recorded lowest RCP and NSSnCl_2 stream which recorded highest RCP. Thus, MDP aliquots stored at ambient temperatures had acceptable quality control results and may be used to diagnose various conditions, especially in low-resource countries with cold chain concerns as was also found in studies done Zulu and others in 2024 (24, 25).

Thokchom and colleagues studied how MDP kit fractionation affects radiopharmaceutical RCP and biodistribution using vial and syringe storage methods (17). The aliquots were kept at -20°C . In their study, the efficacy and RCP of ^{99m}Tc -MDP were compared to those of a traditional process without fractionation. Fractionated ^{99m}Tc -MDP in the vial and syringe had $>95\%$ RCP although by day eight, RCP had dropped to 83.6% and 88%, respectively. Biodistribution studies and image quality assessments were conducted on a total of 100 patients (16). The differences in preparation matrices in terms of variations in normal saline composition and preparation methods could have influenced oxidation rates. Also, the storage conditions and container integrity in terms of differences in vial sealing, oxygen exposure, and handling may have contributed to faster degradation in their study. Dhingra and others assessed the RCP of MDP, Di Mercapto Succinic Acid (DMSA), and Di-Thylenetriamine Penta Acetate DTPA kits, which averaged 95%, 91%, and 95%, respectively (13). They examined 90 samples all together (30 of each) after adding normal saline and refrigerating the aliquots in evacuated vials at -20 to -30°C for 1 to 15 days. Bayomy and colleagues studied Egyptian approaches to lower MDP kit prices. After 30 days, the RCP was tested (13). The aliquots were effectively maintained with an average radiochemical purity of 98.56% for fractions maintained between -20 and -28°C in non-oxygenated vials and 97.15% for fractions maintained between 0 and $+4^\circ\text{C}$ (14). Successful biodistribution studies localized in the region of interest was seen in the human subjects (14).

5.0 LIMITATIONS TO THE STUDY

1. The sample size of control animals was relatively small, which may limit the generalizability of the findings.
2. Imaging was performed using planar scintigraphy rather than more advanced modalities such as SPECT, which could provide improved spatial resolution and quantitative capability.

3. Ambient storage conditions varied between 16–38°C, introducing potential variability in environmental exposure.
4. The study was conducted in animal models, and no clinical (human) data were included, limiting direct translation to patient care.

6.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In conclusion, knowing that antimicrobial resistance (AMR) is a global concern, infectious diseases require accurate diagnosis in order to successfully treat them. Deep-sited infections are hard to diagnose hence Radiopharmaceuticals (RPs) can be employed to solve this problem. This study assessed the use of ambient stored MDP aliquots for infectious illness diagnosis. The biodistribution investigations showed good localization in the region of interest, which meant that these aliquots may be usable. Further research can be done to compare the cost of fractionated MDP to unfractionated MDP, more studies on MDP aliquots stored at ambient conditions can be done for longer than eighteen days period, and also in hotter areas of Zambia using a SPECT gamma camera to assess biodistribution perhaps in actual human patients. This study demonstrates that 99mTc-MDP aliquots can maintain acceptable radiochemical purity under ambient conditions ranging from approximately 16°C to 38°C for up to 18 days. These findings suggest that, in resource-limited settings with unreliable cold-chain infrastructure, carefully prepared and handled MDP aliquots may be safely utilized within this temperature range, provided quality control measures are maintained. This has important implications for reducing radiopharmaceutical wastage, improving access to nuclear medicine services, and informing policy on cold-chain flexibility in low-resource environments.” However, Future studies should address these limitations by incorporating larger sample sizes, advanced imaging modalities, controlled environmental conditions, and clinical validation.

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